

ANTHROPONYMY, ANTHROPONYMICS OR ANTHROPONOMASTICS

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Abstract. *Anthroponymy of group and population names includes the study of demonyms (names of localized populations), ethnonyms (names of ethnic groups), as well as tribal names and clan names.*

Key word: *anthroponyms, andronyms, anthroponymists, ethnonyms, demonyms.*

АНТРОПОНИМИЯ, АНТРОПОНИМИКА ИЛИ АНТРОПОНОМАСТИКА

Аннотация. *Антропонимия групповых и популяционных названий включает изучение демонимов (названий локализованных популяций), этнонимов (названий этносов), а также племенных названий и родовых названий.*

Ключевые слова: *антропонимы, андронимы, антропонимы, этнонимы, демонимы.*

Anthroponymy, anthroponymics or anthroponomastics from Ancient Greek *ἄνθρωπος* *anthrōpos* / 'human', and *ὄνομα* *onoma* / 'name') is the study of *anthroponyms*, the proper names of human beings, both individual and collective. Anthroponymy is a branch of onomastics.

Researchers in the field of anthroponymy are called *anthroponymists*. Since the study of anthroponyms is relevant for several other disciplines within social sciences and humanities, experts from those disciplines engage in anthroponymic studies, including researchers from the fields of anthropology, history, human geography, sociology, prosopography, and genealogy.

Anthroponymists are required to follow certain principles, rules and criteria when researching anthroponyms. The methods used for research are divided into two major categories: the collecting of anthroponymic information and the analysis and interpretation of anthroponyms. The collection of anthroponymic information includes: inscriptions, documents, onomastics-tax records, dictionaries, phone books, monographs, and websites, which are used afterward for mapping purposes. The analysis and interpretation of anthroponyms take into account the processing of the collection of the information gathered, which consists of linguistic analysis, comparative-historical method, geographical method, and statistical method.

Anthroponyms of individuals can also be classified according to gender. Names of human males are called *andronyms* (from Ancient Greek ἀνήρ / man, and ὄνομα / name), while names of human females are called *gynonyms* (from Ancient Greek γυνή / woman, and ὄνομα / name).

Anthroponymy of group and population names includes the study of demonyms (names of localized populations), ethnonyms (names of ethnic groups),^[10] as well as tribal names and clan names.

There are several specific terms and processes related to anthroponymy, like:

- *anthroponymization*, a process when an anthroponym is formed from an appellative, like when a surname is created from the name of one's occupation, thus forming an occupational surname. Such surnames are common in most languages, including English: *Smith* (from smith), *Miller* (from miller), *Thatcher* (from thatcher), *Shepherd* (from shepherd), or *Potter* (from potter).
- *deanthroponymization*, a process when an anthroponym becomes an appellative, like when the surname of the inventor Louis Braille was used to create a name for the writing system for the visually impaired persons (braille).
- *transonymization* of anthroponyms into toponyms, a process when a human proper name is used to form a toponym (proper name of a locality; place name), thus creating an *anthropotonym*, like when the name of Alexander the Great was used to create several *astionyms* (city names), including name for the newly created city of Alexandria in the ancient Hellenistic Egypt, or when the surname of Christopher Columbus was used to create several *choronyms* (region names), including names for Southamerican state of Colombia, and Canadian province of British Columbia.
- *transonymization* of toponyms into anthroponyms, a process when toponyms (place names) are used to form human names (anthroponyms), thus creating various *topoanthroponyms*. Many surnames are created in that way, and they are known as toponymic surnames. Most demonyms (names for localized populations) are *topoanthroponyms* by formation, since they are usually created from toponyms, and also some ethnonyms are *topoanthroponyms* too (those that are formed from toponyms, and thus referred to as *topoethnonyms*). For example, geographic designations for the region of *Black Mountain* (Montenegro) and frontier region of *Ukraina* (Ukraine) were used to create not only demonyms for general populations for those regions, but also ethnonyms for modern ethnic Montenegrins and ethnic Ukrainians.

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